

Physical Endurance And Fitness Levels Of College Students Through Increased Gym Engagement In PATHFIT Courses At St. Bridget College Batangas City

Lalaine C. Ramirez¹

1 – Golden Gate Colleges

ramirezlalaine@gmail.com / 0009-0002-8981-1338

Publication Date: June 2, 2026

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.20503330**

Abstract

This study, titled “Physical Endurance and Fitness Levels of College Students Through Increased Gym Engagement in PATHFIT Courses at St. Bridget College, Batangas City,” explores the impact of gym participation on students’ physical fitness and performance in PATHFIT courses. It examines how gym utilization influences cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength, and endurance, as well as the challenges faced in gym access and participation. Findings revealed that students “often” use gym facilities and actively engage in PATHFIT workouts, leading to improved endurance, strength, and motivation. However, challenges such as academic workload, limited time, safety concerns, and low intrinsic motivation persist. The study concludes that consistent gym participation enhances fitness and promotes positive exercise attitudes, though motivation is largely extrinsic. It recommends fostering self-motivated fitness habits, improving facilities and scheduling, and integrating motivational and peer-support strategies in PATHFIT instruction.

Keywords: *Physical Endurance, Fitness Levels, Gym Engagement, PATHFIT Courses, College Students, Exercise Motivation*

Introduction

As the focus on physical wellness and holistic development continues to grow, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has established CMO No. 39, Series of 2021 which mandates colleges to offer Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) Courses as a part of the General Education Curriculum. The objective of the CMO is to promote and foster lifelong fitness, physical literacy and the building of healthy lifestyle habits among college students through a structured PE program. Incorporating fitness gym participation into the PATHFIT program represents a significant advancement toward achieving these aims, particularly regarding improving students' physical performance as well as their level of involvement and overall health.

This study aimed to enhance college students' performance in PATHFIT by promoting and analyzing their engagement with fitness gym facilities. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of utilization of fitness gyms among college students enrolled in PATHFIT courses in terms of:
 - 1.1. frequency of gym sessions;
 - 1.2. type of fitness activities; and
 - 1.3. student participation and engagement?
2. How does gym utilization affect students' performance in PATHFIT tasks in terms of:
 - 2.1. cardiorespiratory endurance;
 - 2.2. muscular endurance, and
 - 2.3. muscular strength?
3. How effective are the fitness levels of the students relative to:
 - 3.1. building stamina and vigor
 - 3.2. improving muscular strength; and
 - 3.3. enhancing muscular endurance
4. What challenges do students encounter in using fitness gyms for completing PATHFIT requirements?
5. Based on the result of the study, what enhancement activities may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a descriptive quantitative design, which involved observing the selected sample in its natural setting to determine what was occurring in a specific situation. The descriptive survey method was used to investigate the level of utilization of fitness gyms among college students enrolled in PATHFIT courses at St. Bridget College, Batangas City.

Subjects of the study

The subjects of this study were first-year college students enrolled in PATHFIT courses at St. Bridget College, Batangas City, during the first semester of the academic year 2025–2026. A total of 196 students were enrolled in PATHFIT classes, and 25.5% of them—equivalent to 50

students—were selected as respondents for the study. The respondents were distributed across five academic programs (BSIT, BSSW, BSBA, and Education).

Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire was designed and validated by experts in MAPEH and education. The instrument measured the following:

- Level of utilization of fitness gyms among college students enrolled in PATHFIT courses in terms
 - a. frequency of gym sessions;
 - b. types of fitness activities; and
 - c. student participation and engagement.
- How gym utilization affects students' performance in PATHFIT tasks, specifically in:
 - a. cardiorespiratory endurance;
 - b. muscular endurance; and
 - c. muscular strength.
- The effectiveness of the students' fitness levels in relation to:
 - a. building stamina and vigor;
 - b. improving muscular strength, and
 - c. enhancing muscular endurance.
- The challenges encountered by students in using fitness gyms to complete PATHFIT requirements.
- Students' recommendations on how to improve their performance through enhanced gym engagement.

To facilitate meaningful interpretation of the computed mean scores, verbal interpretations were assigned based on pre-established score ranges. A Likert scale was utilized for this purpose.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher first secured permission from the college dean of St. Bridget College through a formal letter. After approval, questionnaires were distributed to respondents via online forms while ensuring anonymity in compliance with the Data Privacy Act. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the survey. Once collected and organized, the data were forwarded to a statistician for analysis and interpretation using appropriate statistical methods.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including composite mean, weighted mean, frequency, percentage, and ranking, were used to summarize and analyze the data. These measures determined the extent of fitness gym utilization, students' performance in PATHFIT tasks, levels of physical fitness, and the challenges encountered, providing a basis for interpretation and recommendations.

Results

Section 1: Level of Utilization of Fitness Gyms

Students frequently utilized fitness gyms as part of their PATHFIT courses, with composite means indicating “Often” across all indicators. Regular gym attendance (WM = 2.63), engagement in various fitness activities (WM = 2.93), and active participation (WM = 3.32) were evident. Students showed strong cooperation, motivation, and application of learned skills. However, participation in extra or voluntary workouts outside class hours was less frequent, indicating that engagement was primarily driven by course requirements rather than personal initiative.

Table 1
Frequency of Gym Sessions

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I regularly attend gym sessions as part of my PATHFIT course.	3.12	Often	1
2. I visit the gym more than once a week to complete my physical activity requirements.	2.74	Often	3
3. I spend sufficient time during each gym session to complete my workout routines.	2.76	Often	2
4. I am consistent in following my workout schedule.	2.6	Often	5.5
5. I allot time for extra workouts outside class hours.	2.24	Sometimes	10
6. I balance my academic schedule to make time for gym attendance.	2.64	Often	4
7. I keep track of my workout frequency to maintain consistency.	2.6	Often	5.5
8. I attend additional gym sessions to improve my overall fitness.	2.4	Sometimes	9
9. I prioritize gym attendance as part of my health and fitness goals.	2.6	Often	5.5
10. I maintain a regular gym routine throughout the semester.	2.6	Often	5.5
Composite Mean	2.63	Often	

Table 1 presents the frequency of gym visits and sessions attended by students as part of their PATHFIT course. It evaluates how often students spend time exercising, which helps them stay active and maintain a healthy lifestyle. The results show a composite mean of 2.63, interpreted as “Often.” This means that, in general, students frequently participate in gym

activities and include them as part of their PATHFIT course requirements. This finding aligns with the study of Sales (2025), who evaluated the implementation of the PATHFIT 1 program at Bicol University and found that the program effectively encouraged students to engage in regular physical activity, improved their overall fitness levels, and enhanced their awareness of the importance of maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

However, the results also indicate that while students actively participate in required gym sessions, they are less consistent in engaging in voluntary workouts. This implies that their motivation to exercise is mostly driven by course requirements rather than personal goals. Consistent with the Self-Determined Behavior Index (SDBI), intrinsic motivation positively influences sustained exercise, while extrinsic motivation has little impact. Thus, promoting self-motivation can encourage students to maintain regular exercise habits beyond class, improving their fitness and overall well-being.

Table 2
Type of Fitness Activities

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I engage in cardio exercises (e.g., treadmill, cycling, jumping rope).	2.9	Often	6
2. I perform resistance or strength training exercises (e.g., lifting weights, push-ups).	2.64	Often	10
3. I include flexibility and stretching routines in my gym sessions.	2.94	Often	5
4. I use gym machines or equipment properly during workouts.	2.82	Often	7
5. I participate in fitness classes or group exercises when available.	3	Often	4
6. I perform exercises targeting both upper and lower body strength.	3.12	Often	2
7. I try new workout programs to enhance my physical performance.	2.72	Often	9
8. I combine aerobics and anaerobic exercises for balanced fitness.	2.8	Often	8
9. I adjust my workout intensity depending on my fitness goals.	3.1	Often	3
10. I choose fitness activities that align with the objectives of PATHFIT.	3.28	Often	1
Composite Mean	2.93	Often	

Table 2 presents the type of fitness activities that students commonly perform during their PATHFIT gym sessions. It assesses how frequently students engage in various exercises

that promote physical strength, endurance, and flexibility. The results show a composite mean of 2.93, interpreted as “Often.” This means that students frequently perform a range of exercises that help them maintain an active and healthy lifestyle. This finding supports the study of Velez (2023), who revealed that the integration of structured and guided fitness instruction within PATHFIT courses significantly improved students’ skill performance.

Overall, the results indicate that students frequently engage in a variety of fitness activities that support both their physical health and the objectives of the PATHFIT course. However, they tend to rely more on familiar routines, such as cardio and flexibility exercises, rather than exploring new or more challenging workouts. This aligns with NZIHG (2025), which emphasizes that exercise programs need to be varied to achieve optimal adaptation, prevent boredom, avoid overuse injuries, and overcome plateaus, while ensuring alignment with the specific fitness goals targeted.

Table 3
Student Participation and Engagement

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I actively participate in all gym activities assigned by my instructor.	3.3	Often	5
2. I am motivated to perform well during gym sessions.	3.26	Often	6
3. I show enthusiasm when participating in fitness activities.	3.28	Often	4
4. I set personal fitness goals and work toward achieving them.	3.24	Often	7.5
5. I maintain focus and effort during each gym session.	3.24	Often	7.5
6. I cooperate well with my classmates during gym-based activities.	3.5	Always	1
7. I seek feedback from my instructor to improve my performance.	3.24	Often	7.5
8. I encourage my peers to stay active and engaged in workouts.	3.24	Often	7.5
9. I apply the techniques and knowledge learned from PATHFIT in my gym routines.	3.48	Often	2
10. I feel a sense of accomplishment after completing my workouts.	3.38	Often	3
Composite Mean	3.32	Often	

Table 3 presents the level of student participation and engagement in gym activities as part of their PATHFIT course. It measures how students demonstrate motivation, cooperation, focus, and goal setting during their physical fitness sessions. The results show a composite mean of 3.32, interpreted as “Often.” This means that, in general, students are highly participative and actively engaged in various gym activities under the PATHFIT program. This finding supports the study of Yang et al (2025), which emphasized personality traits are associated with college students’ exercise motivation. Specifically, Extraversion and Neuroticism influenced exercise behavior partially through self-efficacy and motivation, while Openness affected exercise behavior solely via motivation. These traits may help explain the high levels of engagement observed in the PATHFIT sessions.

Overall, the results show that students are actively engaged and motivated in their PATHFIT gym activities, with strong cooperation, application of learning, and enthusiasm toward fitness. However, there is room for improvement in areas related to self-management, goal setting, and peer encouragement. These findings align with the study of Langøy et al. (2024), who found that when students’ needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are supported in physical education settings, their engagement and long-term participation in physical activity significantly increase.

Section 2: Effects of Gym Utilization on PATHFIT Performance

Gym utilization positively influenced students’ physical performance. Results showed improvements in cardiorespiratory endurance (WM = 3.26), muscular endurance (WM = 3.26), and muscular strength (WM = 3.21), all interpreted as “Agree.” Students reported increased stamina, faster recovery, improved strength, and better ability to perform physical tasks. Regular participation in structured exercises contributed to enhanced overall fitness and physical efficiency.

Table 4.
Cardiorespiratory Endurance

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I have improved my ability to sustain aerobic activities through regular gym use.	3.18	Agree	9
2. I can perform longer physical activities without getting easily tired.	3.18	Agree	9
3. I can feel that my breathing and stamina have greatly improved.	3.26	Agree	3.5
4. I experience faster recovery after intense physical activities.	3.26	Agree	3.5
5. I can maintain steady breathing during long exercises.	3.24	Agree	6.5
6. I have improved my overall cardiovascular fitness through consistent workouts.	3.3	Agree	2
7. I feel less exhausted after completing PATHFIT activities.	3.26	Agree	3.5
8. I can engage in prolonged physical tasks with better endurance.	3.24	Agree	6.5
9. I can feel my heart rate return to normal beat after exercising.	3.24	Agree	6.5
10. I feel more energetic and physically prepared for daily activities.	3.4	Agree	1
Composite Mean	3.26	Agree	

Table 4 presents the level of cardiorespiratory endurance of students as a result of their regular participation in gym activities and PATHFIT sessions. It measures the students' ability to perform prolonged physical activities, maintain stamina, and recover efficiently after exercise. The results show a composite mean of 3.26, interpreted as "Agree." This indicates that students generally perceive improvement in their endurance, stamina, and overall cardiovascular fitness due to consistent engagement in gym workouts. This finding supports the study of Okilanda et al. (2024), which revealed that structured endurance training among university students significantly improves cardiorespiratory fitness, body composition, and muscular strength, leading to enhanced oxygen utilization and reduced fatigue during physical activity.

Table 5
Muscular Endurance

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I can perform multiple repetitions of exercises without fatigue.	3.08	Agree	10
2. I have improved my ability to maintain effort during workouts.	3.34	Agree	3
3. I notice increased endurance in my daily physical activities.	3.36	Agree	2
4. I can complete my PATHFIT exercises without early exhaustion.	3.24	Agree	5. 5
5. I have noticed that my muscles recover faster after prolonged workouts.	3.22	Agree	7
6. I can perform circuit or interval training with improved stamina	3.24	Agree	5. 5
7. I can handle longer durations of moderate to high-intensity exercises.	3.2	Agree	8
8. I experience less muscle strain compared to when I first started.	3.42	Agree	1
9. I can maintain proper form and technique even during long sets.	3.18	Agree	9
10. I have developed muscle endurance that enhances my performance in sports and other physical activities.	3.32	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.26	Agree	

Table 5 presents the level of muscular endurance among students engaged in PATHFIT courses and regular gym workouts. It assesses how well students can sustain muscle performance during prolonged physical activity, resist fatigue, and recover after exercise. The results show a composite mean of 3.26, interpreted as “Agree,” indicating that students generally perceive improvements in their muscular endurance through consistent gym participation. This finding aligns with Masagca (2024), who reported that a 10-week whole-body calisthenics program significantly enhanced muscular endurance in untrained college students, demonstrating improvements in exercises such as push-ups, planks, and wall-sit through consistent resistance and bodyweight training.

Table 6
Muscular Strength

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. I have noticeably improved my muscle strength through gym engagement.	3.26	Agree	3
2. I can lift heavier weights or perform more challenging exercises.	2.98	Agree	10
3. I have become stronger since I started engaging in regular gym activities.	3.16	Agree	6.5
4. I can perform strength-based exercises more efficiently.	3.24	Agree	5
5. I have improved my body composition, gaining increased muscle tone.	3.16	Agree	6.5
6. I can apply my strength to complete PATHFIT physical tasks with ease.	3.28	Agree	2.5
7. I have developed stronger core and limb muscles through consistent training.	3.22	Agree	6
8. I can perform physical demanding exercises	3.16	Agree	4
9. I have developed better posture and body control through strength training.	3.28	Agree	2.5
10. I have improved my overall strength, which has enhanced my daily physical performance.	3.32	Agree	1
Composite Mean	3.21	Agree	

Table 6 presents the level of muscular strength among students engaged in their PATHFIT courses and regular gym activities. It evaluates how gym engagement has helped students improve their ability to exert force, perform strength-based exercises, and enhance overall physical performance. The results show a composite mean of 3.21, interpreted as “Agree.” This indicates that students generally perceive an improvement in their muscle strength due to consistent gym participation. This finding supports the review by Cheatham et al. (2024), which reported that well-supervised resistance training programs for youth significantly improve strength outcomes and long-term muscle function.

Section 3: Effectiveness of Fitness Levels

Students demonstrated effective improvement in overall fitness levels, including stamina and vigor (WM = 3.12), muscular strength (WM = 3.24), and muscular endurance (WM = 3.16), all interpreted as “Often.” Findings showed increased energy, reduced fatigue, improved posture, and enhanced physical performance. These results indicate that PATHFIT activities and gym engagement effectively support students’ physical development and promote healthy lifestyles.

Table 7
Building Stamina and Vigor

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. My regular gym workouts help me feel more energetic throughout the day.	3.08	Often	7.5
2. My energy level throughout the day has improved because of consistent gym workouts.	3.06	Often	9
3. My overall body endurance has noticeably improved since joining the gym.	3.1	Often	6
4. My participation in gym activities has boosted my vitality and enthusiasm for exercise.	3.18	Often	3
5. I experience increased stamina and physical alertness.	3.16	Often	4
6. I can perform physical activities for longer periods without feeling easily fatigued.	3.12	Often	5
7. I recover faster after performing intense physical activities.	3.08	Often	7.5
8. I can complete longer PATHFIT sessions without losing focus or energy.	3.2	Often	2
9. I rarely experience fatigue during physical activities.	3.02	Often	10
10. I feel more active and less tired in performing daily routines.	3.22	Often	1
Composite Mean	3.12	Often	

Table 7 presents the results on the effectiveness of gym engagement in building students’ stamina and vigor, showing a composite mean of 3.12, interpreted as “Often.” This indicates that students generally experience improvements in stamina, vitality, and overall physical alertness

due to consistent gym workouts. This finding supports the study of Promoting exercise behavior and cardiorespiratory fitness among college students based on the motivation theory (Li et al., 2022), which demonstrated that students' exercise behavior significantly mediates the relationship between exercise motivation and cardiovascular fitness.

Table 8
Improving Muscular Strength

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. My improved muscular strength helps me perform better in PATHFIT tasks.	3.36	Often	1
2. My arms and legs have become noticeably stronger.	3.2	Often	8
3. My posture and balance have improved as my strength increased.	3.32	Often	2
4. My core strength has significantly improved through consistent training.	3.3	Often	3
5. I have developed stronger muscles through regular gym engagement.	3.16	Often	9
6. I can now perform more physically demanding exercises than before.	3.22	Often	7
7. I can lift or handle heavier weights during workouts.	3.02	Often	10
8. I have gained confidence in performing strength-based exercises.	3.26	Often	5.5
9. I can execute PATHFIT activities that require strength with ease.	3.26	Often	5.5
10. I feel physically capable of accomplishing more challenging fitness goals.	3.28	Often	4
Composite Mean	3.24	Often	

Table 8 presents the level of muscular strength among students engaged in PATHFIT courses and regular gym activities. It assesses how consistent gym participation enhances students' strength, posture, balance, and overall physical capability. The results show a composite mean of 3.24, interpreted as "Often." This indicates that students generally experience improvement in their muscular strength as a result of consistency. These findings align with recent evidence: for example, Zhao et al. (2022) demonstrated significant gains in muscular strength, power and endurance following a school-based strength training intervention. Similarly, Qi (2023) highlighted how core strength training in college physical education improves muscle capacity, posture and balance.

Table 9
Enhancing Muscular Endurance

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. My endurance during workouts and physical tasks has improved since I started going to the gym.	3.12	Often	8
2. My ability to perform continuous movements has improved.	3.22	Often	3.5
3. My muscles have adapted to longer training durations.	3.16	Often	6.5
4. My overall endurance contributes to better athletic and academic performance.	3.06	Often	9
5. I can sustain physical effort for longer durations without exhaustion.	3.24	Often	1.5
6. I can complete exercise routines with greater consistency and control.	3.16	Often	6.5
7. I rarely experience muscle fatigue during repetitive exercises.	3.02	Often	10
8. I can maintain the same level of performance throughout my workout sessions.	3.18	Often	5
9. I can participate in endurance-based PATHFIT activities more efficiently.	3.24	Often	1.5
10. I notice improved flexibility and resistance to fatigue.	3.22	Often	3.5
Composite Mean	3.16	Often	

Table 9 presents the level of muscular endurance among students engaged in PATHFIT courses and regular gym activities. It evaluates how consistent gym participation helps students sustain physical effort, resist fatigue, and adapt to longer training sessions. The results show a composite mean of 3.16, interpreted as “Often.” This indicates that students generally experience improvements in endurance, energy, and resistance to fatigue due to regular gym workouts. This finding supports the study of Khatkhat et al. (2020), who reported that circuit training significantly improved cardio-respiratory endurance and stamina among college students participating in structured fitness programs.

Section 4: Challenges in Using Fitness Gyms

Students frequently encountered barriers to gym utilization (WM = 2.72, “Often”). The most common challenges included lack of time due to academic workload, difficulty balancing responsibilities, and psychological factors such as low confidence and safety concerns. Other issues involved limited access to facilities, financial constraints, and inconsistent schedules. Despite these challenges, most students still maintained participation in gym activities.

Table 10
Challenges in Using Fitness Gyms

Statements	WM	VI	RANKING
1. Lack of time to attend gym sessions due to academic workload.	3.04	Often	1
2. Limited access to gym facilities or unavailable equipment.	2.72	Often	7
3. Lack of motivation or interest in attending gym sessions.	2.68	Often	8
4. Difficulty balancing academic responsibilities and fitness requirements.	2.8	Often	2
5. Inadequate supervision or guidance from instructors during workouts.	2.44	Sometimes	10
6. Safety concerns or fear of injury while using gym equipment.	2.78	Often	3.5
7. Lack of peer or instructor support during gym activities.	2.54	Often	9
8. Financial constraints that limit my ability to maintain a gym routine.	2.7	Often	5.5
9. Inconsistent gym schedules or overcrowded gym facilities.	2.7	Often	5.5
10. Lack of confidence or self-consciousness when performing workouts in public.	2.78	Often	3.5
Composite Mean	2.72	Often	

Section 5: Tailored Interventions Proposed to Improve Gym Engagement in PATHFIT Exercises Among First-Year College Students.

Structured Orientation and Fitness Education. A structured orientation program is recommended for first-year students to familiarize them with gym equipment, exercise techniques, and the health benefits of regular participation in PATHFIT exercises.

Objectives:

1. Demonstration sessions led by trained fitness instructors.
2. Informational materials highlight the importance of physical fitness, cardiovascular health, and strength development.
3. Short workshops on goal-setting and personal fitness planning.

Providing Flexible Access and Supportive Materials. This intervention focuses on removing barriers to gym engagement, such as limited schedules, lack of information, or unfamiliarity with exercises. It ensures students have adequate resources and time to participate effectively.

Objectives:

1. Provide students with opportunity to use gym equipment.
2. Extend gym hours or offer flexible scheduling to accommodate different student timetables.
3. Designated time slots for PATHFIT students to ensure sufficient space and support

PATHFIT class utilizing the equipment of wellness fitness gym to remove the barriers to gym engagement, such as limited schedules, lack of information, or unfamiliarity with exercises.

Personalized Fitness Plans for Diverse Activities. Develop personalized fitness plans tailored to individual preferences, fitness levels, and goals. Plans will integrate a variety of exercises (cardio, strength, flexibility) to maintain engagement and optimize physical improvements.

Objectives:

1. Create fitness routines that align with student interests and current fitness levels.
2. Promote consistent engagement by varying exercises to prevent monotony.
3. Track student progress in cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength, and flexibility to reinforce motivation.

FITNESS PLAN				
CARDIO	MUSCULAR STRENGTH	MUSCULAR ENDURANCE	FLEXIBILITY	CARDIO
BRISK WALKING 1 hr and 30 minutes (10k steps)	SQUAT 2 sets of 10 reps	PLANK 2 sets of 30 seconds	SEATED HAMSTRING	BRISK WALKING 1 hr and 30 minutes (10k steps)
JOGGING 30 minutes	CURLS UP 2 sets of 10 reps	SQUAT 2 sets of 12 reps	SIDE STRETCH	JOGGING 30 minutes
ZUMBA 30 minutes	PLANK 2 sets of 20 seconds	WALL SIT 2 sets of 45 seconds	ARM STRETCH	ZUMBA 30 minutes

Mike Andrei P. Tumambing

PATH FITH				
Cardio	Strength	Endurance	Flexibility	Other Exercise
 Head Rolls				
 Split Squats				
 High knees				

Personalized Fitness Plans for diverse activities to tailor individual preferences, fitness levels and goals

Promoting Self-Motivated Fitness Activities Beyond Class Requirements. To encourage students to engage in physical activity beyond PATHFIT requirements, first-year college students were tasked to try to enroll in a gym outside the campus. This intervention aims to motivate students to actively participate in self-directed fitness activities, fostering the development of lifelong exercise habits. By exploring different fitness environments and exercise routines independently, students can take ownership of their physical health, enhance their motivation, and experience the benefits of regular exercise beyond the academic setting.

Objectives:

1. To motivate the students to highly engage in exercise and gym activities beyond the academic requirements of PATHFIT.
2. Cultivate lifelong exercise habits by exposing students to diverse workout routines and independent fitness experiences.
3. Foster personal responsibility for health and well-being, emphasizing the benefits of consistent physical activity for mental, social, and physical wellness.

Physical activity at home to encourage students to engage physical activity beyond
PATHFIT class

Gym Based Activity Outside the Campus

Integrating Motivational Strategies, Peer Support, and Individualized Feedback. To sustain engagement and participation in PATHFIT gym sessions, instructors will incorporate motivational strategies, peer support systems, and personalized feedback. This holistic approach ensures that students feel encouraged, supported, and guided throughout their fitness journey. Peer collaboration promotes accountability, while individualized feedback helps students identify progress and areas for improvement.

Objectives:

1. Apply motivational techniques such as goal-setting, recognition, and reinforcement.
2. Encourage peer-to-peer support through group workouts and fitness challenges.
3. Provide constructive, individualized feedback to enhance student performance.
4. Foster teamwork, confidence, and continuous improvement in gym engagement.

Wellness Activity in PATHFIT Class

Wellness Activity in PATHFIT Class

Discussion

The findings revealed that students “often” use gym facilities and actively engage in PATHFIT workouts, leading to improved endurance, strength, and motivation. This is consistent with existing literature emphasizing that structured physical activity and consistent exercise engagement contribute to improved physical fitness, overall health, and academic performance among college students.

The level of gym utilization, particularly in terms of frequency, types of activities, and student engagement, indicates that students actively participate in required fitness tasks. However, the lower involvement in voluntary or additional workouts suggests that students’ motivation is

largely influenced by course requirements rather than intrinsic factors. This highlights the need to promote self-motivation and encourage students to adopt exercise as part of a long-term healthy lifestyle beyond academic obligations.

The identified challenges—such as time constraints, academic workload, limited access to facilities, and psychological barriers—reinforce the importance of designing fitness programs that are flexible, inclusive, and responsive to students' needs. Addressing these barriers through improved scheduling, enhanced support systems, and accessible facilities can further strengthen student participation and engagement.

Overall, the improvement in students' fitness levels, combined with active participation in gym-based activities, suggests that gym engagement within the PATHFIT program is an effective approach to promoting physical development and wellness. However, further studies involving a larger sample size and extended duration are recommended to validate these findings and explore strategies for sustaining long-term student engagement in physical activity.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that increased gym engagement in PATHFIT courses is an effective strategy for enhancing the physical fitness and endurance of college students at St. Bridget College. It promotes positive attitudes toward physical activity; however, students' motivation is largely driven by course requirements rather than intrinsic interest. Moreover, factors such as academic workload, safety concerns, and limited facilities remain significant barriers to consistent participation, highlighting the need for more supportive and accessible fitness programs.

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